

Marketing Digitalization to Increase the Potential of Supporting Aspects of the Teaching Factory Model in Vocational Higher Education

Retno Sari Mahanani
Department of Agribusiness Management
Jember State Polytechnic
Jember, Indonesia

Ridwan Iskandar
Department of Agribusiness Management
Jember State Polytechnic
Jember, Indonesia

Wenny Dhamayanthi *
Department of Agribusiness Management
Jember State Polytechnic
Jember, Indonesia

Linda Eka Widyatami
Department of Agribusiness Management
Jember State Polytechnic
Jember, Indonesia

Andarula Galushasti
Department of Agricultural Production
Jember State Polytechnic
Jember, Indonesia

* Corresponding Author:

Wenny Dhamayanthi, Department of Agribusiness Management, Jember State Polytechnic, Jember, Indonesia

Abstract:- Showing teaching factories can be a consensus of information advancement, in authentic conditions to base the workforce hole between the insight given and the states of the security. Sweats to develop security-predicated knowledge have also begun to be developed through the construction of teaching factories. Predicated on the description of the phenomenon over, to meliorate business performance at the teaching factories Agrimart Polije, disquisition is demanded on the digitization of the marketing teaching factories Agrimart Polije. This investigation includes a quantitative and descriptive investigation that was purposefully carried out at the State Polytechnic of Jember's Department of Agribusiness Management. Testing ways are carried out by styles without openings, videlicet purposeful slices, or predicated on specific considerations. This disquisition is a geek analysis approach to find the combination of marketing digitalization generalities following current conditions.

Keywords:- Agrimart; Marketing Digitalization; Strategy Management; Teaching Factory.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the prominent vocational schools that contributes to the generation of professed and competent individuals is Jember State Polytechnic. It corresponds to the fantasy of the Jember State Polytechnic Institute, which will become a Superior State Polytechnic Institute in Asia in 2035. Enhancing innovative and competitively employable instruction is one of its goals. Implementing product-

predicated classes and relating and matching with sedulity are two of the developed strategies. Through the construction of a Teaching Factory, efforts to develop knowledge based on sedulity have also begun. Teaching factories can be a general way to develop knowledge in factual parts to fill in the knowledge gap between what is taught and how things are. There have been as many as 23 teaching factories broadcast across multiple services and the Integrated Development Unit of the Jember State Polytechnic since the beginning of time [1].

The Department of Agribusiness Management is one of the Departments at the Jember State Polytechnic. Which has innovated the conformation of teaching factories. it is to support the performance of the class by furnishing assiduity-rested knowledge services and direct practices that are homogenized tallying to assiduity needs as trouble to develop ingenious knowledge and operative practices. The introducing Teaching Factory that the Agribusiness Management Department will constitute is the Teaching Factory Agrimart Polije, with a seat area on marketing services. The plan to establish a teaching factory is rested on a product-rested class erected in the Department of Agribusiness Management, where this teaching factory can be used to develop knowledge styles for the Department of Agribusiness Management's courses and practicums. It is hoped that this Teaching Factory will also serve as a position or method for faculty evaluation. it is in line with the elaboration of faculty test tricks that are being carried out in the Agribusiness Management Department, videlicet the "active marketers" scheme, which is the result of a link and match with the assiduity.

Suppose exploration is a continuity of the study disquisition or projection form and the introductory frame/master plan in the conformation of the Teaching Factory Agrimart Polije. In that case, it needs to be developed on the generality of marketing digitalization. The Agrimart Polije Teaching Factory's sedulity, the absence of supporting human resources (HR), and the actuality of the Agribusiness Management Department's installations in the form of laboratories (the Entrepreneurship Laboratory, the Computer Laboratory, and the Business Communication Laboratory) can be utilized as value additions. Additionally, the Agrimart Polije Teaching Manufactories will be able to work together and synergize with several teaching factories that were previously located on the Jember State Polytechnic campus, particularly in terms of marketing. It's to contribute and adapt to technological developments that have entered all operations and business lines. It can accelerate the achievement of the vision and charge of the Jember State Polytechnic.

This study includes several papers from a previous study on teaching factories that were published in international and public journals. Several previous research findings, including Malika's, are used to identify factory operation factors. [1], which analyzes the activity of showing the production line by arranging, coordinating, directing, overseeing, and surveying. The study also discussed supporting factors and obstacles to factory operation education to improve knowledge quality. [2]. Related to operation aspects, also to strengthen included theoretical studies of operation principles [3]. Also, concerning the previous investigation into the agricultural teaching factory masterplan, which was based on marketing services. Sumarwan says that this literature review also focuses on marketing strategies and generalities. [4], which talks about strategic marketing, and Kemper [5], explains the factual consumption and marketing hypotheticals held by dealing academics.

II. METHODS

This quantitative descriptive exploration was conducted intentionally at the Department of Agribusiness Management, Jember State Polytechnic. Data collection was carried out utilizing questionnaires and conducting Focus Group Discussions (FGD) with the directors of the Agribusiness Management Department. consequently, from this stage of exertion, the precedence of the Agrimart Polije teaching factory marketing program grounded on digital technology can be arranged following the precedence of the programs contained in the Jember State Polytechnic. The position of the

study was determined designedly in the Department of Agribusiness Management, Jember State Polytechnic, and also as a follow-up to the former exploration. The stopgap in the future is the perpetration of a teaching factory interpretation evaluation grounded on the place of thickness and felicity of enforcing the digital marketing strategic bout at the Agrimart Polije teaching factory. This exploration was conducted from March to December 2022. The population in this study is the director of the Department of Agribusiness Management, the Head of the Jember State Polytechnic, artificial mates in husbandry, and others. The slice fashion is carried out with a nonprobability system. The intentional slice system is grounded on special considerations knowledge, capability, and experience in the field under study. Primary data is collected through direct interviews with eatery directors through valid and dependable questionnaires. Secondary data is sourced from data or information possessed by applicable agencies (both published and unpublished), as well as books, diurnals, or colourful forms of publication, as stated in the bibliography. The dissection fashion exercised is the geek dissection system. A geek dissection determines the most applicable indispensable program to be applied. SWOT dissection is a shape of dissection of the internal and foreign conditions of an association/ society, which will also be exercised as a base for intended work strategies and programs. The logical tools exercised in formulating and prioritizing strategies are IFE, EFE, IE, and SWOT matrices[6].

III. RESULTS

Overview of Jember State Polytechnic: Jember State Polytechnic is one of the prominent vocational schools that contributes to the generation of professionals and experts. It is a continuation of the fantasy of the Jember State Polytechnic Institute, which will become a Superior State Polytechnic Institute in Asia in 2035. Enhancing innovative and competitively employable instruction is one of its goals. Implementing product-based classes and relating and matching with sedulity are two of the developed strategies. Through the construction of a Teaching Factory, efforts to develop knowledge based on sedulity have also begun. Teaching factories can be a generalization of knowledge evolution in factual parts to fill in the faculty gap between what is taught and how things are. There have been as many as 23 teaching factory broadcasts across multiple services and the Academic Support Unit of the Jember State Polytechnic until this point.

A. Internal factor evaluation matrix

TABLE I. IFE MATRIX

No	Internal Factors	Rating	Weight	Score
Strength				
1	Availability of teaching materials according to competence	4	0.090	0.360
2	Modern product management	3	0.088	0.264
3	Have creative human resources	4	0.095	0.380
4	Cooperation with industry parties	4	0.087	0.348
5	Have quality product results	3	0.095	0.285
6	The product has begun to be known by the public	3	0.085	0.255
Weakness				
1	Have not met consumer demand appropriately	2	0.070	0.210

2	Lack of product promotion	2	0.075	0.225
3	Low production financing	2	0.085	0.255
4	Still narrow marketing reach	1	0.075	0.225
5	Product marketing channels have not been maximized	2	0.087	0.261
	Lack of HR knowledge and insights		0.067	0.201
	Total		1.000	2.945

This IFE matrix is prepared based on the results of interviews conducted with the Management of the Agribusiness Department as the manager of the Agrimart teaching factory startup. Weighting is done by comparing each of the internal factors of the teaching factory to get the factors that take precedence. Furthermore, the rating is carried out by looking at the actual condition of the teaching factory's potential to get the main strengths and weaknesses in the teaching factory development area.

In the IFE matrix above, it can be concluded that the main strength of teaching factory development is to have creative human resources, with a score of 0.380. Meanwhile, the main weakness of teaching factory development is that the product marketing channel has not been maximized, with a

score of 0.261. Hence, the total combined score for the internal factors of teaching factory development is 2,945, which means that the development of the teaching factory has strengths and weaknesses above the average standard of 2.50.

B. External factor evaluation matrix

This EFE matrix is collected and grounded on interviews conducted with several applicable agencies, academic interpreters, and implicit residents. Weighting is done by comparing each of the external factors of the teaching factory to get the factors that take priority. likewise, the standing is carried out by looking at the factual response of the implicit development of the teaching factory to the openings and pitfalls that live or will be faced.

TABLE II. EFE MATRIX

No	External Factors	Rating	Weight	Score
Opportunity				
1	Increasing public consumption of teaching factory products	4	0.095	0.380
2	The abundance of promotional media	4	0.098	0.392
3	The market potential is quite large	3	0.095	0.285
4	Increasing consumer demand for teaching factory production	4	0.087	0.261
Threat				
1	The influx of new technologies	1	0.155	0.465
2	Lower prices of competitors' products	2	0.175	0.350
3	The onslaught of promotion of competing teaching factory products	2	0.165	0.495
4	The abundance of marketing locations for competitors' products	2	0.175	0.350
	Total		1.00	2.978

In the EFE matrix over, it can be concluded that the main occasion factor for the teaching factory development is the number of promotional media, with a score of 0.392. Meanwhile, the main trouble that the development of teaching factories has watched out for is the ferocious creation of contending teaching factory products, with a score of 0.495. The total concerted score for external factors for teaching factory development is 2,978, which means that the development of teaching factories in the face of openings and pitfalls can be said to be good because it has exceeded the average standard of 2.50.

C. Internal-external matrix

According to David [7] IE (Internal External) matrix positions the colorful divisions of an association in a nine-cell view. Each division within an association must produce an IFE Matrix and an EFE Matrix concerning the association. The IE matrix is grounded on two crucial confines the total IFE weight score on the x-axis and the total EFE weight score on the y-axis. The total weight score attained from similar

divisions allows the arrangement of the IE Matrix at the enterprise position. On the x-axis of the IE Matrix, a total IFE weight score of 1.0 to 1.99 indicates a weak internal position; a score of 2.0 to 2.99 is considered moderate, and a score of 3.0 to 4.0 is strong. also, on the y-axis, the total EFE weight score of 1.0-1.99 is looked down upon; a score of 2.0-2.99 is considered moderate, and a score of 3.0-4.0 is high. The IE matrix can identify nine enterprise strategy cells, but the nine can be grouped into three main strategies [7].

Fig. 1. SWOT Matrix

Fig. 2. IE Matrix

Based on the discussion of the factors of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats above, it can be concluded that the value of IFE and EFE can be concluded to determine the strategy for developing a teaching factory at Agrimart State Polytechnic of Jember. Therefore, the grand strategy matrix can be determined through the SWOT analysis quadrant in the IFE calculation of 1.48 (x-axis) and the EFE calculation of 1.43 (y-axis). As for the calculation results of IFE and EFE, it is known that the development of the teaching factory is in quadrant 1. In this case, it shows that the development of the teaching factory has quite good strength and has a reasonably good opportunity. The total weighting result of the IFE matrix is 2.945, and the EFE matrix is 2.978. Then the result is mapped into the IE matrix, where the x-axis comes from the total value of the IFE matrix and the y-axis comes from the total value of the EFE matrix. So that the IE matrix above can be concluded that the position of teaching factory development is in cell V, the divisions included in cell V can be adequately handled through a strategy of maintaining and maintaining (hold and maintain). Strategies that can be used are market penetration, market development, and product development. Market penetration and product development are the two most widely used strategies.

TABLE III. SWOT ANALYSIS

	Strength (S)	Weakness (W)
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Availability of teaching materials according to competence 2. Modern product management 3. Have creative human resources 4. Cooperation with industry parties 5. Have quality product results 6. The product has begun to be known by the public 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Have not met consumer demand appropriately 2. Lack of product promotion 3. Low production financing 4. Still narrow marketing reach 5. Product marketing channels have not been maximized 6. Lack of HR knowledge and insights
Opportunity (O)	SO	WO
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increasing public consumption of teaching factory products 2. The abundance of promotional media 3. The market potential is quite large 4. Increasing consumer demand for teaching factory production 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Improving product marketing through print and electronic media (S1, S2, O2, O3) 2. Conducting product offerings and cooperation with several manufacturers (S5, S6, O4) 3. Collaborating with industry to apply research results (S4, S5, S6, O1) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increase marketing reach by increasing the number of productions (W2, W4, O3, O4) 2. Structuring and improving the training system as a whole, collaborating and building networks with teaching factory practitioners (W1, W4, W5, W6, O1, O2, O3)
Threat (T)	ST	WT
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The influx of new technologies 2. Lower prices of competitors' products 3. The onslaught of promotion of competing teaching factory products 4. The abundance of marketing locations for competitors' products 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Industry, government, community, and media can synergize with the creation of programs that lead to increased competence (S1, S4, S6, T2, T4) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Improving industry capabilities through technology and knowledge transfer (W5, W6, T1, T3) 2. Increase production appropriately (W1, W2, T2, T3)

IV. CONCLUSION

The findings in this study are the possibility or potential aspects supporting the vocational education teaching factory model that will emerge, such as human resources, product, partnership, and marketing. Then it needs to be developed on the concept of digitalization of marketing. It is primarily in the development of the concept of marketing digitalization in teaching factories to be able to contribute and adapt to technological developments that have penetrated all lines of management and business, as well as accelerating the achievement of the vision and mission of the Jember State Polytechnic. Development of facilities for business results and teaching factory support that is developed and adjusted to the activities and hierarchy of needs for these facilities. The need to develop the potential of other service sectors, such as mentoring and publication of scientific papers, as well as maximum utilization of existing potential in a sustainable manner. The contribution of this research is to present the concept of marketing digitalization that can improve business performance at the Teaching Factory Agrimart Polije. It is to hopefully adapt to technological developments that have penetrated all management and business lines, as well as accelerate the achievement of the vision and mission of the Jember State Polytechnic.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The Ministry of Research Technology and Higher Education, the Republic of Indonesia, supports this Research at Jember State Polytechnic.

REFERENCES

- [1]. U. E. Malika, D. Kurniawati, and A. Sutantio, "Master Plan Teaching Factory Agrimart Polije," 2021.
- [2]. R. Risnawan, "Manajemen Teaching Factory Dalam Upaya Pengembangan Mutu Pembelajaran di SMK," *Media Manaj. Pendidik.*, vol. 2, no. 1, p. 13, 2019, doi: 10.30738/mmp.v2i1.3549.
- [3]. R. L. Felsted, D. R. Richter, and N. R. Bachur, "Rat liver aldehyde reductase," *Biochem. Pharmacol.*, vol. 26, no. 12, pp. 1117–1124, Jun. 1977, doi: 10.1016/0006-2952(77)90054-5.
- [4]. U. Sumarwan, *Strategi Pemasaran Jasa Pendidikan dalam Meningkatkan Nilai Jual Madrasah*, Kesatu. Bogor: IPB Press, 2015.
- [5]. J. A. Kemper, P. W. Ballantine, and C. M. Hall, "Sustainability worldviews of marketing academics: A segmentation analysis and implications for professional development," *J. Clean. Prod.*, vol. 271, p. 2020, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.122568.
- [6]. F. R. David, *Strategic Management Manajemen Strategis Konsep*. Bandung: Salemba Empat, 2011.
- [7]. F. R. David, *Strategic Management*. New Jersey: Pearson Education, Inc, 2011.